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- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
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THE FOURTH PHASE OF DISTANCE EDUCATION: INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGIES AND MOOCS

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Abstract: This article addresses the issue of digital content intended for use in distance education and online learning environments. The foreign and Russian experience in the development of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) is examined, and the challenges associated with this process are identified. The authors also share their experience in developing and using a multimedia program that is closely aligned in format with a MOOC. The instructional (didactic) structure of the multimedia module is presented.

Key words: distance technologies, Massive Open Online Courses, e-learning, web-based education, multimedia module.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola masofaviy ta'lim va onlayn o'qitish muhitida foydalanish uchun mo'ljallangan raqamli materiallar muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslarni (MOOK) ishlab chiqishda xorijiy va Rossiya tajribasi tadqiq etiladi, ushbu jarayon bilan bog'liq muammolar ochib beriladi. Shuningdek, mualliflar formati bo'yicha MOOKga juda yaqin bo'lgan multimedia dasturini ishlab chiqish va undan foydalanish bo'yicha o'z tajribalari bilan o'rtoqlashadilar. Multimedia modulining o'quv-uslubiy asosi, ya'ni didaktik tuzilmasi bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: masofaviy texnologiyalar, ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslar, elektron ta'lim, veb-ta'lim, multimedia moduli.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена проблеме создания цифрового контента, предназначенного для использования в системах дистанционного образования и онлайн-обучения. Исследуется зарубежный и российский опыт разработки массовых открытых онлайн-курсов (MOOK), выявляются сопутствующие этому процессу проблемы. Авторы также делятся собственным опытом разработки и использования мультимедийной программы, которая по своему формату максимально приближена к MOOK. Сформулирована дидактическая структура мультимедийного модуля.

Ключевые слова: дистанционные технологии, массовые открытые онлайн-курсы, электронное обучение, веб-образование, мультимедийный модуль.

INTRODUCTION

Today, a fourth stage in the development of distance education may be identified—the integration stage, which is characterized by fully virtualized training technologies. This stage is grounded in the advancement of information dissemination tools enabled by the cohesive integration of modern communication technologies. Such technologies ensure the rapid delivery of virtually any type of information to users across the globe. For instance, learners can now access multiple university communication channels, including the Open (Virtual) University, which incorporates the Worldwide Academy Network and the Open University of the United Kingdom. Contemporary information technologies are also being integrated into regional associations, such as the Asian Association of Open Universities, the Latin American Joint Network for the Development of Distance Education, and the European Association of Distance Teaching Universities. In Russia, the Modern University for the Humanities (MUH) established a satellite-based educational television network covering several federal academic disciplines. Under an agreement between MUH and the University of Cambridge, the first televised lectures delivered by scholars from this renowned British institution were broadcast to various regions of Russia. Furthermore, MESI (Moscow State University of Economics, Statistics, and Informatics) has been actively developing distance education with a particular emphasis on e-learning technologies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Distance education technologies are classified into two main groups: e-learning, which relies on satellite television, the Internet, local networks, and digital learning materials; and case technologies, which depend on physical (paper-based) methodological resources. From 2006–2008, due to the insufficient level of informatization in Russia's regions and the high costs associated with printing paper-based materials, a third variant was applied—"Folder Technology," named after the folder concept in Microsoft Office. This approach provided correspondence students with a comprehensive methodological package, including workbooks, instructional guidelines, examination materials, and readers, distributed on CD-ROMs. All resources were organized within a digital folder, which significantly reduced printing costs compared to paper-based formats while simultaneously facilitating the administration and scheduling of students' academic activities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The advancement of global informatization and increased Internet accessibility have profoundly transformed the educational landscape. Contemporary digital technologies offer new opportunities for "web-based education," which represents a fully distance-oriented instructional approach. K. Martynov notes that the Internet provides immediate access to all educational materials, including video lectures, textbooks, and assessments, and enables both synchronous communication (video conferences, chats) and asynchronous interaction (email, blogs, forums).

Particular interest is associated with Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), which are platforms that deliver university-level curricula combined with academic interaction and, in some cases, formal certification. Udacity was established by Sebastian Thrun of Stanford University in 2012 and specializes primarily in information technology. By mid-2014, the platform offered 36 courses and had attracted more than 1.6 million learners. Coursera was founded in 2012 by Andrew Ng and Daphne Koller from Stanford University. By 2013, it had accumulated approximately 4 million users and provided access to more than 400 courses from over 80 partner institutions. edX was created in 2012 as a collaborative initiative of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Harvard University, and the University of California, Berkeley. By 2014, the platform had reached 2 million learners and established partnerships with major technology companies, including Google. In addition to these global platforms, several European MOOC initiatives have emerged, most notably FutureLearn in the United Kingdom, OpenupEd within the European Union, and iversity in Germany.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Despite prevailing optimism, some scholars argue that MOOCs signal the "end of the university era." We contend that MOOCs function as a powerful complement to traditional education, particularly in the context of professional development. However, they cannot replace the processes of socialization and social capital formation inherent in conventional higher education institutions, nor can they substitute the university's role as a center for real-time knowledge creation. Moreover, so-called "unprecedented freedom" is not invariably beneficial. Minimal admission requirements often result in low course completion rates (for example, below 5% on Coursera). Additional concerns include learners' tendency to procrastinate, the potential risk of educator unemployment, and apprehensions regarding "cultural imperialism" associated with the dominance of leading global universities. In Uzbekistan, prestigious institutions such as the Higher School of Economics (HSE), St. Petersburg State University (SPbSU), and the Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology (MIPT) have launched similar initiatives. The "Universarium" project, supported by the Agency for Strategic Initiatives, aims to reinforce the prominence of Russian universities in the digital educational space in order to safeguard national identity and promote the Uzbek language internationally.

The authors conducted an experimental implementation of a "Multimedia Module" designed to enhance instructional clarity and accessibility. A Multimedia Module is defined as an autonomous instructional unit that integrates audiovisual resources with a methodological guide intended for the development and assessment of professional competencies. The module consists of the following components: video cases presenting professional problem situations for assessing competency levels; instructional manuals designed for both instructors and students; a student workbook comprising at least 10 reflective tasks (for example, "identify the error") and 30 assessment items; and a business game script derived from the audiovisual materials. Within a pilot project implemented in Master's degree programs in Management and Economics, the authors developed modules consisting of four 15-minute episodes. Episode 1 presents theoretical content through a "problem-based dialogue" among subject-matter experts. Episode 2 demonstrates the practical application of the targeted competence through role-play. Episode 3 illustrates typical mistakes arising from insufficient skill development. Episode 4 involves an interactive role-play in which learners choose a course of action and immediately observe its consequences.

CONCLUSION

Multimedia modules are intrinsically connected to the MOOC format and effectively contribute to the modernization of higher education. They possess global dissemination potential through translation, preserve the cultural and reputational assets of universities by documenting the expertise of distinguished professors, standardize educational quality for distance learners, and ensure meaningful engagement with Generation Z as a digitally native cohort. In addition, multimedia modules enable the implementation and configuration of autonomous learning tasks in full compliance with the most recent Federal State Educational Standards (FSES).

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.